

ANNOTATION GUIDELINES FOR CLINICAL ENTITIES - CARMEN-I CORPUS

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SUMMARY

As part of the collaboration between the Barcelona Supercomputing Center and the Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, 500 anonymised clinical reports of different types have been manually and collaboratively annotated with six clinical entities: diseases, symptoms, procedures, drugs, species, and humans. The extraction of this information from hospital reports has several use cases, the major one being the automatic structuring of the reports. The rules are based on previous work carried out by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center team: the DisTEMIST corpus for diseases, SympTEMIST for symptoms and findings, ProcTEMIST for procedures, DrugTEMIST for drugs and LivingNER for species and humans.

These guidelines compile the rules followed for the annotation of clinical entities, serving as a summary of previously published annotation guidelines.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This guide describes the annotation of mentions of diseases, symptoms, procedures, drugs, species, and humans in the CARMEN-I corpus, which consists of anonymised clinical reports.

The CARMEN-I corpus

CARMEN-I is a collection of reports written at the Hospital Clínic de Barcelona during the COVID-19 pandemic (March 2020 to early 2022). CARMEN-I is composed of 2000 reports of different types (discharge, transfer, radiology, etc.) that have been anonymised and validated by a team of natural language processing experts, linguists, and clinicians.

Out of 2000 reports, a subset of 500 reports has been semantically annotated with six clinically relevant entities: DISEASES, SYMPTOMS, PROCEDURES, DRUGS, SPECIES, and HUMANS.

Named entity recognition

Entity recognition in text is a natural language processing technique that focuses on identifying and classifying types of information of the same semantic class within a text. These entities can be, for example, names of people, organisations, locations, or dates. The main goal of an entity recognition task is to extract relevant and structured information from unstructured texts, which facilitates the automatic understanding and analysis of large volumes of textual data.

In the clinical domain, entity recognition in texts plays a crucial role. Clinical reports, generated daily in large quantities by hospitals and health centres, contain a lot of information that is unstructured and, to a certain extent, "lost". The application of medical entity extraction and classification systems helps us to retrieve this information, allowing it to be standardised into clinical terminologies so that it can be automatically structured. Entity recognition in medical records also supports many other higher-level tasks such as the identification of key information for tasks like coding diagnoses and procedures, epidemiological

surveillance, discovery of medical knowledge from a specific set of reports or even clinical decision making.

One of the major obstacles to the application of these technologies is the lack of annotated data to train and evaluate quality systems. Artificial intelligence systems learn from the examples provided by the annotated data, so we need quality data, annotated by domain experts, varied, and similar to the type of document where the systems are to be applied (clinical reports).

In Spanish, the Natural Language Processing for Biomedical Information Analysis group at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (under funding from the Spanish government's Language Technology Plan and other projects) has been releasing open resources for the detection and normalisation of information in the clinical domain for years. These resources use published clinical cases and patient descriptions similar in content and form to clinical reports. Although not exactly reports, clinical cases have the advantage that they do not contain sensitive data, so they can be shared freely. All resources are generated following annotation guidelines validated by clinical experts and refined by the iterative annotation of multiple documents.

The resources reviewed for this guide are:

- **DisTEMIST** is a resource for automatic disease detection and is normalised using the SNOMED CT ontology. The corpus uses documents from the SPACCC corpus, a collection of 1000 clinical cases from different specialties hand-picked by clinical experts. The guidelines are a 28-page document explaining in detail the annotation of diseases.

DisTEMIST was presented as part of a *shared task* in the BioASQ 10 workshop at the CLEF 2022 conference.

The DisTEMIST corpus is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6408476>.

DisTEMIST guides are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6458078>.

More information on the task, corpus and guidelines can be found at <http://temu.bsc.es/distemist>.

- **ProcTEMIST/MedProcNER** is a resource for the automatic detection of procedures and is normalised using the SNOMED CT ontology. The SPACCC corpus documents are also used for the corpus, the annotation being complementary to the DisTEMIST corpus. The guidelines are a 31-page document explaining in detail the annotation of medical procedures.

ProcTEMIST was presented as part of a *shared task* called MedProcNER in the BioASQ 11 workshop at the CLEF 2023 conference.

The ProcTEMIST corpus is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7817745>.

The ProcTEMIST guides are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7817666>.

More information on the task, corpus and guidelines can be found at <https://temu.bsc.es/medprocner>.

- **SympTEMIST** is a resource for the automatic detection of symptoms, signs and findings and is normalised using the SNOMED CT ontology. The SPACCC corpus documents are also used for the corpus, with the complementary annotation being DisTEMIST and ProcTEMIST.

SympTEMIST was presented within a *shared task* as part of BioCreative VIII at the AMIA 2023 conference.

The SympTEMIST corpus is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8413866>.

The SympTEMIST guidelines are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8246440>

More information on the task, corpus and guidelines can be found at <https://temu.bsc.es/symptemist>.

- **DrugTEMIST** is a resource for the automatic detection of drugs and is normalised using the SNOMED CT ontology. This corpus also uses the documents of the SPACCC corpus, completing the SPACCC annotation with three other complementary clinical entities (diseases, procedures and

symptoms). DrugTEMIST corpus and guidelines are still pending publication.

DrugTEMIST was presented within a *shared task* as part of BioASQ 12 at the CLEF 2024 conference.

The DrugTEMIST corpus is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948354>.

The DrugTEMIST guidelines are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11065432>

More information on the task, corpus and guidelines can be found at <https://temu.bsc.es/multicardioner/>.

- **LivingNER** is a resource for the automatic detection of species (pathogens, living beings) and humans, as well as their normalisation to a specialised terminology called NCBITaxonomy. The corpus uses 1000 clinical cases from different specialties (such as oncology, infectious diseases, travel medicine, urology or paediatrics), chosen for their relevance to the annotation. The guidelines are a 51-page document explaining the annotation of pathogens and humans, as well as their normalisation using the NCBITaxonomy.

LivingNER was presented within a *shared task* as part of the IberLEF workshop at the CLEF 2023 conference.

The LivingNER corpus is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6376662>.

The LivingNER guides are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6385162>.

More information on the task, corpus and guidelines can be found at <https://temu.bsc.es/livingner/>.

As part of the collaboration between the Barcelona Supercomputing Center and the Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, these guidelines are used and adapted for the annotation of real anonymised hospital reports from the CARMEN-I corpus. This involves the validation of the guidelines described above in a purely clinical environment. The annotation is also partly done in conjunction with hospital

specialists. These specialists participated in the annotation of a part of the corpus and gave their impressions on the annotation rules, enriching them with their knowledge on less defined or specific aspects of the COVID pandemic. The annotation was then completed and reviewed by the BSC in a second step.

Description of clinical entities

In short, this guide includes six clinical entities: DISEASES, SYMPTOMS, PROCEDURES, DRUGS, SPECIES, and HUMANS. These are briefly described below:

- **DISEASES:**

We understand diseases as clinical conditions that affect the normal functioning of the body and that have a certain extension in time.

The annotation of this label is based on the DisTEMIST corpus. The label name in Spanish is ENFERMEDAD.

Examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "hidradenitis suppurativa", "malnutrition", "bipolar disorder" or "subocclusive syndrome".

- **SYMPTOMS:**

This label covers three distinct clinical concepts: symptoms (understood as manifestations of clinical conditions that are often self-reported and may be subjective); signs (manifestations observed by health professionals); and findings (test results, such as laboratory tests and X-rays).

The annotation of this label is based on the SympTEMIST corpus. The label name in Spanish is SINTOMA.

Some examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "The patient has no pain. No thermic sensation. No cough. No dyspnea".

PROCEDURES:

Procedures are actions or interventions performed by health professionals in order to diagnose or treat diseases and health problems.

The annotation of this corpus is based on the MedProcNER/ProcTEMIST corpus. The label name in Spanish is PROCEDIMIENTO.

Examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "a plastic biliary prosthesis is placed"; "ABDOMINAL ECOGRAPHY is conducted".

- **DRUGS:**

We use this label for specific products, compounds or substances with a defined molecular composition and a therapeutic purpose.

The annotation of this label is based on the DrugTEMIST corpus. The label name in Spanish is FARMACO.

Some examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "HABITUAL TREATMENT: Bictarvy 1 CP/d"; "Quetiapine 300 mg/12h".

- **SPECIES:**

Species describe living beings (with the exception of humans, which have their own label). This label includes animals (lives with a cat); food (peach allergy); and, above all, pathogens (bacteria, viruses, fungi, parasites).

The annotation of this label is based on the LivingNER corpus. The label name is SPECIES.

Examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "HCV INFECTION"; "pneumococcal infection and Coronavirus OC43".

- **HUMANS:**

This category includes mentions of people in the text in a general way. It can be applied to the patient and their family, to healthcare workers, and epidemiological contacts, or even job positions, co-workers, the police, or firefighters.

The annotation of this label is based on the LivingNER corpus. The label name in Spanish is HUMANO.

Some examples of this label taken from the corpus are: "82-year-old woman"; "Retired, worked as a lawyer. Lives with grandparents (main carer). Has 1 child".

Information about these guidelines

These guidelines describe, as a summary, the main annotation rules for six clinical entities: DISEASES, SYMPTOMS, PROCEDURES, DRUGS, SPECIES and HUMANS. Each entity has its own section, plus a section of general rules that applies to every entity.

As mentioned above, the rules for each entity are taken from the annotation guidelines of previous *Gold Standard* corpora developed by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center. Therefore, this guide can also serve as a summary of the other guides mentioned above, serving as a reference for the simultaneous annotation of different types of clinical entities.

For the creation of CARMEN-I, we worked with many clinical specialists from Hospital Clínic. For this reason, we would like to thank: Helena Ariño, Elena Calvo, Elisa Asensio, Xavier Borrat, Xavier Pastor, Antonio López, Maria Ángeles Marcos, Maria Jesús Bertrán, Artur Conesa and Santiago Frid.

Regarding the colour coding in the examples: correct annotations related to each rule are marked in **blue**; correct annotations that are not related to the rule are marked in **bold**; incorrect annotations are marked in **red**. Occasionally we will underline a part of the annotation to clarify the rules. The examples used in the guidelines are a mixture of real examples from the CARMEN-I corpus and examples from previous guides.

2. GENERAL RULES

	Rule	Example
Every label		
General Rules	[G1] Comprehensiveness All instances of an entity must be annotated.	A chest X-ray was performed. The chest X-ray showed bilateral nodules
	[G2] Between sentences Annotations may not span more than one sentence.	Pain in RIF. Ultrasound shows no signs suggestive of appendicitis.
	[G3] Spelling mistakes Misspellings are also annotated.	Swimming pool rebilitation (<i>Swimming pool rehabilitation</i>)
	[G4] Complete words Words must be annotated completely. Words cannot be annotated partially.	MRI / MRI
	[G5] Determiners Determiners are not annotated: articles (the), demonstratives (this, that.), numerals (one, two, three), etc.	A hysterectomy with bilateral oophorectomy is performed. ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION in treatment with three antihypertensive drugs , the patient improves.

	<p>[G6] Punctuation marks No punctuation mark at the beginning or the end of an entity should be annotated, except closing parentheses.</p>	<p>Stenting is ruled out due to age, and treatment is limited to antiplatelet agents, and observation.</p>
	<p>[G7] Languages If different languages are studied, entity mentions in every language are annotated (e.g., English and Spanish).</p>	<p>Symptom onset date: 7/9/21 with digestive symptoms (digestivo)</p>
	<p>[G8] Word limit We will not annotate as a single entity very long mentions if there are more than 6 words between the two relevant parts.</p>	<p>Drainage complicated by agitation of the right lateral abscess Replacement after more than two weeks of continuous visits to the emergency room of the pacemaker</p>
	<p>[G9] Negations Denied mentions are annotated, but no negation words are included unless they are part of a clinical concept.</p>	<p>The patient has no diarrhoea We performed a colectomy without polypectomy. Non-contrast CT Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma</p>
	<p>[G10] Uncertainty Expressions of (un)certainty such as "suspected of", "suggestive of", "that appears to be", "looks like", "compatible with", etc., are not included in the annotations.</p>	<p>image suggestive of parathyroid adenoma They probably performed a colonoscopy, he explains that the test results were normal. Frontal epidural collection that appears to be infectious POSSIBLE ANTIPHOSPHOLIPID SYNDROME.</p>
	<p>[G11] Non-patient</p>	<p>Family history of parents with hypertension</p>

	<p>Mentions that do not refer to the patient are also annotated.</p>	<p>Mother with metastatic breast cancer in contact with covid positive patients</p>
	<p>[G12] Abbreviations Abbreviations that refer to a clinical concept are annotated. If they appear together with their long form, they are also annotated separately.</p>	<p>COPD GOLD 4C with multifactorial hypoventilation with BIPAP at night Thoracic-abdominal computerised tomography (CT) scan (In this example, there are two annotations: "Thoracic-abdominal computerised tomography" and "CT").</p>
	<p>[G13] Span overlapping It is possible to annotate the same piece of text with more than one different semantic label.</p>	<p>In the interaortocaval node, 6 adenopathies were isolated [DISEASE]. (In this example, two labels should be annotated: a <i>disease</i> [the presence of adenopathies in the interaortocaval node] and a <i>procedure</i> [the surgical isolation of adenopathies in this anatomical area]).</p>
	<p>[G14] Anaphora We will not annotate anaphora and cataphora (references to an entity using pronouns).</p>	<p>Personal history of resection of fibroadenoma in the right breast 4 months before coming to our department. With this unique antecedent...</p>
	<p>[G15] Time expressions and age Time expressions and references to age are not included in the annotation (unless they fall in</p>	<p>Nocturnal enuresis [DISEASE] persists until the age of 13 years. Right lower lobe pneumonia in 2021</p>

	<p>between two relevant concepts such as a disease and its anatomical area and do not violate the rule G8).</p>	<p>HIV INFECTION STAGE C3 diagnosed in 1990</p>
	<p>[G16] Subject The subject of the sentence or the person who suffers/reports the disease, takes medication, undergoes a procedure, etc., should be excluded from the annotations.</p>	<p>Mother with metastatic breast cancer Endomyocardial biopsy on brother confirmed the diagnosis.</p>
	<p>[G16] Measurements References to measurements/dimensions are not included in the annotation (unless they are in the middle of two relevant parts such as a procedure and its anatomical area).</p>	<p>We finished by implanting another everolimus stent that was 2.5 x 12 mm. A liver 2x2cm tumour was found.</p>

3. RULES FOR DISEASES

	Rule	Example
Label DISEASE		
Positive Rules	<p>[DIS-P1] General expressions Very general terms such as "disease", "problem", "syndrome", etc. are annotated if and only if they are accompanied by qualifiers such as anatomical locations, names of persons, causative organisms/substances/pharmaceutical products, etc.</p>	<p>ANXIOUS-DEPRESSIVE SYNDROME in medical treatment</p> <p>Polycystic kidney disease</p> <p>Complete remission of the disease</p> <p>Cranial CT scan ruled out acute pathology.</p> <p>bacteriemia problem</p>
	<p>[DIS-P2] Anatomical area The anatomical area where the disease occurs is included in the annotation, avoiding reference points such as "proximal", "distal", "frontal", etc.</p>	<p>CALCIFIED MEDIASTINAL ADENOPATHIES</p> <p>COLORRECTAL POLIPES</p>
	<p>[DIS-P3] Laterality The laterality of a disease is included in the annotation when talking about the heart, the colon, the hypochondrium, the iliac fossa, the flank and every type of intracranial pathology.</p> <p>In the rest of the anatomical areas, it should not be annotated unless the mention becomes</p>	<p>The patient has ischaemic foci in the right cerebral hemisphere.</p> <p>some doubtful right lenticular lacunar infarction</p>

	<p>meaningless if it is not included.</p> <p>Bilaterality should always be annotated.</p>	<p>liver dextrocardia in the <u>left</u> hemiabdomen and gastric bubble in the <u>right</u> hemiabdomen.</p> <p>Diagnosis of <u>bilateral pneumococcal pneumonia</u></p> <p><u>bilateral renal lithiasis</u></p>
	<p>[DIS-P4] Disease cause When the cause or the origin is expressed together with a disease, it should be included in the annotation.</p> <p>When listing pathogens as a cause we shall limit ourselves to the shortest possible form (genus+species) and exclude sensitivities, resistances, serotypes, etc.</p>	<p>BILATERAL INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA FROM <u>SARS-CoV-2</u></p> <p>COMPLICATED URINARY TRACT INFECTION WITH <u>E. FAECALIS</u> that is beta-lactam-resistant</p> <p>upper gastrointestinal bleeding due to <u>oesophageal varices</u></p> <p>Chronic kidney disease due to <u>polycystic disease</u> treated with haemodialysis</p> <p>multifactorial <u>malnutrition</u></p>
	<p>[DIS-P5] Pathogenesis When the pathogenesis of a disease is expressed (e.g., "immune", "hormonal", "hereditary", etc.), it should be included in the annotation.</p>	<p>A diagnosis of <u>hereditary bipolar disorder</u> is made and a treatment with lithium salts is started.</p> <p><u>AUTOIMMUNE HEPATITIS/PRIMARY BILIARY CHOLANGITIS/RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS</u></p>
	<p>[DIS-P6] Order If possible, the terms should include the order of diseases in the causal chain ("primary",</p>	<p>Cranial CT: <u>secondary tumour</u></p>

	<p>"secondary", etc.). Sometimes the ordering element is part of the name of the disease (<i>primary biliary cholangitis</i>).</p>	<p>AUTOIMMUNE HEPATITIS/PRIMARY BILIARY CHOLANGITIS/RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS</p>
	<p>[DIS-P7] State Whenever possible, the annotations should include the state of the disease ("acute", "recurrent", "chronic", "terminal", etc.).</p>	<p>Benzathine penicillin prophylaxis for recurrent streptococcal pharyngotonsillitis</p> <p>CHRONIC LOW BACK PAIN</p>
	<p>[DIS-P8] Start Whenever possible, annotations should include the onset or the start of the disease ("adult onset", "paediatric onset", "infant onset", "early", "embryonic", "puerperal", etc.).</p>	<p>Early-onset Parkinson's</p> <p>Late-onset alpha-1,4-glucosidase deficiency</p> <p>Juvenile acne</p> <p>Postmenopausal urethral atrophy</p>
	<p>[DIS-P9] Severity Annotations may include ONLY the following severity adjectives: "mild", "moderate", "severe" and "critical".</p>	<p>History of critical pneumonia requiring hospitalisation</p> <p>mild neutropenia</p>
	<p>[DIS-P10] Responses Adjectives referring to the response to a treatment should be included in the annotation when they specify a subtype of a disease (e.g. "refractory").</p>	<p>History of renal cysts, cholecystectomy, refractory hypertension</p> <p>Early restart of the second cycle due to good tolerance to treatment.</p>

	<p>However, treatment responses alone should not be recorded.</p>	
Negative Rules	<p>[DIS-N1] Stages Stages, scales or clinical classifications should not be included in the annotation.</p> <p>However, numerals that are part of the name of the disease (as in types of diabetes) are annotated.</p>	<p>Stage C3 HIV infection Clear cell renal carcinoma with capsular infiltration consisting of a Fuhrman grade 2 Diabetes mellitus II ERC SHARPENED AKIN II</p>
	<p>[DIS-N2] Temporality The temporal context (age, "old", "recent", "intermittent", etc.), as well as frequency quantifiers and ratios, should not be included in the annotation.</p> <p>The concept ex- shall be included in the case of toxic habits.</p>	<p>An old scar on the abdominal wall was observed. heavy smoking (20-30 cigarettes/day for more than 10 years) Ex-smoker since 1992 (120 packages/year) and ex-alcohol since 2006</p>
	<p>[DIS-N3] Episodes References to the episodes of the clinical entity (e.g. "episode of", "first episode", "old episode", etc.) should not be included in the annotations unless they are accompanied by a qualifying adjective that sufficiently describes the type of episode.</p>	<p>Second episode of macroscopic haematuria No other previous thromboembolic episodes</p>

	<p>[DIS-N4] Inferences Inferences should not be made when annotating, so we will not annotate clinical findings that indicate the existence of a disease.</p>	<p>8-10% ejection fraction</p> <p>(In this example there is no explicit mention of a disease, although an ejection fraction of less than 15% is indicative of congestive heart failure).</p>
	<p>[DIS-N5] Evolution Evolutionary changes in the state of the diseases ("improvement", "worsening", "increase", "persistence", etc.) are not annotated.</p>	<p>Worsening of pneumonia Decreases the size of the lung injury</p> <p>Right upper lobe lung mass increase</p>
	<p>[DIS-N6] Pathogens Pathogenic organisms (viruses, fungi, bacteria, parasites, etc.) that appear by themselves should not be annotated.</p>	<p>Gonococci grow in conjunctival discharge culture and penicillin is administered.</p> <p>GASTRO-ESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE with <u>H. pylori</u></p>
	<p>[DIS-N7] Social determiners No mention of demographics, life stages, risk factors, lifestyles, geriatric assessments or other social determiners of health should be annotated.</p>	<p>Retired, worked as a lawyer. Lives with his grandparents (main carer). Has 1 child</p> <p>48-year-old morbidly obese woman with a sedentary lifestyle and poor adherence to a Mediterranean diet, consulted for skin lesions after eating molluscs.</p> <p>Patient aged 84 years, lives alone, comes to the hospital with a femoral fracture.</p>

Special Rules	<p>[DIS-S1] Disease conventions To homogenize the annotation criteria, the following concepts should be annotated as diseases:</p> <p>"allergy", "toxicity", "adverse reaction", "adenopathy", "tumour infiltration", "cystic", "deficit of...", "thrombus", "dilatation of..."</p>	<p>No known drug allergies</p> <p>ALLERGY to sulphonamides and ASAs</p> <p>Axillary and supraclavicular adenopathy can be observed.</p> <p>Abdominal cystic mass</p> <p>without dilatation of the excretory tract</p>
	<p>[DIS-S2] Symptoms conventions To homogenize the annotation criteria, the following concepts are considered symptoms and should not be annotated as diseases:</p> <p>"healthy", "toxicity", "paraesthesia", "mediastinal enlargement", "voiding condition", "constitutional syndrome", "worsening of...", as well as concepts related to death.</p>	<p>Died 3 days after admission</p> <p>Neonatal death</p> <p>Worsening of the renal function</p>
	<p>[DIS-S3] Hemogram results Regarding hemogram results, the following concepts shall always be considered as a disease: "anaemia", "bicytopenia", "tricytopenia", "pancytopenia".</p>	<p>leukoerythroblastic reaction without neutropenia and thrombopenia</p> <p>pancytopenia attributed to chronic amiodarone therapy</p>
	<p>[DIS-S4] Mutations Genetic mutations shall not be annotated except where they are part of the name of the disease.</p>	<p>No EGFR mutation was found and no ALK translocation was performed at that time.</p>

		Marfan syndrome with FBN1 gene mutation
	<p>[DIS-S5] Addictions Addictive behaviours shall always be considered as a disease.</p>	<p>Ex-smoker Smokes marijuana every weekend</p>
	<p>[DIS-S6] Absence of organs The absence of organs shall be annotated as a disease in the various forms in which it is expressed.</p>	<p>The ultrasound did not show any tubes, ovaries or uterus. The CT scan of the brain showed the absence of corpus callosum</p>
	<p>[DIS-S7] Injuries The word "injury" plus a noun complement (adjective, prepositional phrase) shall be annotated as a disease, as well as the word "injury" on its own.</p>	<p>Cystic injury space occupying injury</p>
	<p>[DIS-S8] Morphological abnormalities Morphological abnormalities that are classified as a disorder in SNOMED-CT are annotated as a disease. The colour and shape of dermatological injuries should be included.</p>	<p>Has been having telangiectasias for one week More than 8 coffee-coloured stains on the limbs</p>

4. RULES FOR SYMPTOMS, SIGNS AND FINDINGS

	Rule	Example
Label SYMPTOM		
Positive Rules	<p>[SYM-PI] Signs and Symptoms</p> <p>We include the doctor's findings during the examination of the patient and the patient's expressions about their health problem.</p>	<p>Increased peristalsis</p> <p>Disoriented and aggressive</p> <p>the patient is disoriented and has a slurred speech, as well as fever.</p> <p>I observe a sweating patient</p> <p>Patient with a history as described above, frail, multi-pathological, that comes from the residence for hallucinations, anasarca and non-productive cough.</p> <p>In the emergency department, the patient has fever, anasarca, shows signs of biventricular CHF, and has no neurological focality.</p> <p>Mentions that he has been living with a relative who has had symptoms and her asymptomatic child</p> <p>During his stay, he shows a respiratory worsening.</p>

[SYM-P2] Test Results

Qualitative descriptions of tests and test results are annotated with this label. The name of the test is included when necessary to interpret the statement. Normal results are also annotated. Quantitative results are not annotated.

COVID +

Blood test with **d-dimer decreasing** with a last result of 2,400 (previous 7,000) and **ferritin increasement**.

Electroencephalogram with high-frequency oscillations

The **pathological report was normal**.

Isolation of Aspergillus fumigatus in sputum culture

Positive perineal smear, administration of ampicillin is recommended.

Negative rovsing and murphy signs

Sediment with no important findings

Normal Hemogram

transferred to the isolation unit where a **positive smear test** was carried out

COLONOSCOPY (18/09): Abundant **dark-coloured liquid debris throughout the terminal ileum** suggesting...

** URGENT GASTROSCOPY (9/09): **Oesophagus without lesions**, cardia located 42 cm from the dental arch. **Stomach with fundus in normal retroversion**. No **blood debris** was found in any of the explored areas.

	<p>[SYM-P3] Imaging tests We will annotate descriptions of imaging tests with this label as long as the described content in the test is not a disease.</p>	<p>Pattern on tarnished glass</p> <p>Hepatic hypoechogenic mass</p> <p>Chest X-ray with vascular redistribution and free costophrenic sinuses.</p> <p>Chest CT: right superior lobe with nodule suspicious for small cell carcinoma.</p>
	<p>[SYM-P4] Exitus Deaths are also annotated as symptoms</p>	<p>Died 3 hours after admission</p> <p>presented progressive clinical worsening and comfort measures were initiated, being exitus vitae on October 15.</p>
	<p>[SYM-P5] Location Whenever possible, we will annotate the anatomical area where the symptom occurs.</p>	<p><u>Cervical mass</u></p> <p>Pain in <u>upper limb</u> and <u>distended abdomen, painful on palpation</u>.</p> <p>Abdomen with pain on palpation of the <u>lower abdomen, predominantly in the hypogastrium</u>.</p>
	<p>[SYM-P6] Ordinals</p>	<p>Cranial CT: secondary mass</p>

	Whenever possible, annotations should include the ordering of the symptoms ("primary", "secondary", etc.).	
	<p>[SYM-P7] State Whenever possible, the annotations should include the state of the disease ("acute", "recurrent", "chronic", "terminal", etc.).</p>	His grandfather had a chronic cough and needed oxygen
	<p>[SYM-P8] Laterality The laterality of a disease is included in the annotation when talking about the heart, the colon, the hypochondrium, the iliac fossa, the flank, and every type of intracranial pathology.</p> <p>In the rest of the anatomical areas, it should not be annotated unless the mention becomes meaningless if it is not included.</p> <p>Bilaterality should always be annotated</p>	<p>Left knee pain</p> <p>Right frontal lobe opacities</p> <p>Bilateral basal condensation</p>
	<p>[SYM-P9] Severity Citations may include ONLY the following severity adjectives: "mild", "moderate", "severe" and "critical".</p>	<p>Moderate ocular redness without visual disturbance</p> <p>Moderate elevation of inflammatory parameters</p>
Negative Rules	<p>[SYM-N1] Daily activities No annotations should be made regarding the patient capacity in terms of daily activities.</p>	<p>Tolerates sitting down</p> <p>Tolerates oral intake of drugs</p>

		Independent for conducting Daily Activities
	<p>[SYM-N2] Temporality The temporal context (age, "old", "recent", "intermittent", etc.), as well as frequency quantifiers and ratios should not be included in the annotation.</p>	<p>Intermittent fever with episodes of night sweats</p> <p>6 days of dyspnoea</p>
	<p>[SYM-N3] "Everything normal except..." The normality of symptoms shall not be annotated if the entity is followed by "except" or similar elements, indicating that normality is not complete.</p>	<p>on physical examination, the external genitalia were normal, except for painful palpation of the nodule.</p>
	<p>[SYM-N4] Anatomical Pathology Pathology results are not annotated due to their complexity.</p>	<p>AP shows solid and microcystic areas with fibrin zones</p>
	<p>[SYM-N5] Descriptions Descriptions that are not an inherent part of the symptom name, or universally recognisable, should be avoided.</p>	<p>Irregular tumour with rounded contours</p> <p>Abdominal ultrasound: hypoechoogenic hepatic mass</p>
Special Rules	<p>[SYM-S1] Conventions for symptoms To homogenise the annotation criteria, the following concepts should be annotated as symptoms: "mass" (except "tumour mass" which is equivalent to tumour), "nodule" (except "tumour nodule" which is equivalent to tumour),</p>	<p>Ultrasound: adrenal mass with ill-defined contours</p> <p>Anteroposterior CXR with calcified nodules in the upper lobes.</p> <p>CBC: anaemia with leukocytosis and neutrophilia.</p>

	"leukocytosis", "neutrophilia", "lymphocytosis".	
	<p>[SYM-S2] Disease Conventions</p> <p>To homogenise the annotation criteria, the following concepts are considered diseases and should not be annotated as symptoms: 'adenopathy', 'anaemia', 'bicytopenia', 'pancytopenia', 'aplasia', 'atelectasis', 'effusion', 'collection', 'ulcer', 'cyst', 'tumour', 'tumour mass', 'tumour nodule', 'dilatation' + anatomical location, 'calcification', 'haematoma'.</p>	<p>Bilateral submental adenopathy</p> <p>A hepatic collection is observed in the segment III</p> <p>right atrial dilatation with tricuspid regurgitation</p>
	<p>[SYM-S3] TNM</p> <p>The TNM oncological staging is considered a symptom</p>	Oesophageal squamous cell carcinoma T4bN+M0
	<p>[SYM-S4] Mutations</p> <p>Genetic mutations are annotated as a symptom</p>	no BCR/ABL gene rearrangement or JAK-2 mutation was detected
	<p>[SYM-E5] Oxygen requirements</p> <p>Mentions of oxygen requirements by the patient are annotated as symptoms, without including in the mention the specific oxygen value if it appears.</p>	<p>Given that this is a multi-pathological patient with oxygen therapy needs, it was decided to admit him to the hospital ward for SARS-CoV-2+ patients.</p> <p>With depletive treatment, the patient shows initial improvement, with reduction of oxygen requirements to 2L nasal lentils and disappearance of bronchospasm.</p>

[SYM-E6] General state changes

General changes in the patient's condition are annotated. However, the evolution of specific symptoms and diseases is not noted.

Chest x-ray 1/11/2023: **significant radiological improvement**, although with **persistence of bilateral interstitial infiltrate** predominantly in the bases.

During admission, after contact with a person affected by COVID-19, he presented **fever** and **progressive respiratory worsening**, requiring VMK up to 60%,

The known **opacities in both lung fields** persist, with **improvement in all of them** with respect to previous studies.

Subsequently, after **clinical/analytical and blood gas improvement** but **persistence of bilateral infiltrates**, a CT scan was performed without showing **organizational changes** and **significant improvement of bilateral infiltrates**.

On 12/11 he presented with an episode of progressive hepatic encephalopathy and a **very marked deterioration of his general condition**.

5. RULES FOR PROCEDURES

	Rule	Example
Label PROCEDURE		
Positive Rules	<p>[PROC-P1] General expressions Very general terms such as "procedure", "examination", "study", "observation" and "monitoring" should be annotated if accompanied by specific qualifiers and anatomical locations.</p>	<p>Histological study of epidermal lesions</p> <p>Fundus examination revealed bilateral problems.</p>
	<p>[PROC-P2] Types of procedures The following types of procedures should be annotated: surgical, diagnostic (e.g. imaging) and preventive. Test batteries should also be annotated, such as 'histopathological study', 'hormone study', 'hemogram' or 'urinalysis'.</p> <p>However, reports are not annotated as procedures, as they describe results, nor are laboratory procedures that result in a single measurement or observation [we will consider these concepts as Observable Entities, not procedures].</p>	<p>surgical resection of nodular tumour in the right epididymis</p> <p>The macroscopic study describes the...</p> <p>The anatomicopathologic report was...</p> <p>Biochemistry: glucose 82 mg/dl</p> <p>MYOCARDIAL PERFUSION TOMOGRAM AFTER PHARMACOLOGICAL AND AT-REST INTERVENTIONS</p> <p>In the ECG study (Gated-SPECT) there seems to be...</p> <p>Date of nasopharyngeal swab for Covid-19: Not done</p>
	<p>[PROC-P3] Anatomical Location The anatomical area where the procedure is</p>	<p>left orchiectomy via the inguinal route</p>

	carried out is included in the annotations.	Cranial CT Approach to the cerebellar abscess
	[PROC-P4] Laterality Laterality in procedures should <u>always</u> be annotated.	Amputation of the left upper limb was performed. A catheter is inserted into the right ureter.
	[PROC-P5] Administration method The administration method ("cutaneous", "nasal", "oral", etc.), and the type of access used to reach the site of the procedure are included in the annotations.	when percutaneous drainage was scheduled oral enteral nutrition
	[PROC-P6] Instruments The instruments and equipment used to perform the procedure are included in the annotations.	Fine needle aspiration was performed. venturi mask 28%. respiratory support with high-flow therapy
	[PROC-P7] Devices Devices and the act of insertion and removal from the body should be included in the annotation.	It was decided to opt for the placement of a spinal neurostimulator 600ml of plasma is infused Placement of an intracranial pressure monitor nasogastric tube removal

	<p>[PROC-P8] Materials This includes materials such as substances, drugs, biological or synthetic materials, etc. used to carry out the procedure.</p>	<p>He subsequently received radiotherapy with cobalt-60 in the pelvis.</p> <p>In contrast-enhanced abdominopelvic CT scanning</p> <p>Hypermobile atrial septum with possible shunt evident on agitated saline bubble test.</p>
	<p>[PROC-P9] Drugs General families and types of drugs, as well as mentions of treatments with them, are annotated as procedures. This rule does not apply to specific drugs, which are annotated with the label <i>DRUGS</i>.</p>	<p>He was on antibiotics for a week</p> <p>Appropriate antibiotic prophylaxis</p> <p>Corticosteroid treatment is decided</p> <p>Vancomycin and hydroelectric replenishment treatment started</p> <p>In case of doubts regarding the patient's psychopharmacological management...</p> <p>When COVID medication ends, prescribe regular medication.</p>
	<p>[PROC-P10] Proper nouns The annotations include proper nouns that are part of surgical interventions and invasive techniques.</p>	<p>Plicature of Kelly</p> <p>Right renal pyeloplasty via the Anderson-Hynes technique was performed</p>
	<p>[PROC-P11] Intentionality For oncological treatments, the intentionality of the treatment shall be included in the</p>	<p>He was subsequently treated with radiotherapy with radical</p>

	<p>annotations.</p>	<p>intent and is now disease free.</p> <p>Complementary radiotherapy is considered</p> <p>adjuvant therapy with adriamycin and ifosfamide schedule for six cycles</p>
	<p>[PROC-P12] Chemotherapy Schedules For oncological treatments with chemotherapy regimens, the acronym of the regimen should be annotated separately.</p>	<p>[Chemotherapy with [FOLFIRI] plus BEVACIZUMAB] was administered.</p>
	<p>[PROC-P13] Anaesthesia In general, we will annotate anaesthesia mentions separately from the rest of the mention.</p>	<p>In flexible cystourethroscopy under epidural anaesthesia</p>
	<p>[PROC-P14] Adjectives Adjectives of procedures are included in the annotation only when they are part of the name or add information on the type of procedure.</p>	<p>The modified Ziehl-Neelsen stain was negative.</p> <p>(In this example, the modified Ziehl Neelsen stain is different from the classical Ziehl Neelsen stain.)</p> <p>Staging bone scan performed</p> <p>(From <i>staging</i> we learn that a scan is done specifically to locate bone metastases).</p>
	<p>[PROC-P15] Treatment</p>	<p>corticosteroid treatment</p>

	<p>The word treatment is annotated when it is accompanied by an adjective without further information. If the type of treatment is specified, it is not included in the annotation.</p>	<p>on treatment with antiplatelet agents</p>
	<p>[PROC-P16] Syntactic forms Often, the text does not directly mention the procedures carried out, but it does talk directly about the results. Therefore, the procedures will be annotated in all the syntactic cases that we find. For example, in the form of a noun phrase (Chest X-ray), an adverb (histologically), etc.</p>	<p>appropriate radiological response Endoscopic findings confirm the suspicion of ulceration. Conclusions: Gammagraphic pattern of dilated cardiomyopathy without evidence of ischaemia. Urine. Ag. Legionella (5/1/2024): Negative achieving 98% vision with contact lenses</p>
Negative Rules	<p>[PROC-N1] Laboratory Medical laboratory procedures where a single measurement or observation is made should not be annotated.</p>	<p>Biochemistry of blood: glucose 145 mg/dl</p>
	<p>[PROC-N2] Drugs Mentions of specific treatments or administration of specific drugs should not be annotated.</p>	<p>We decided to discontinue the baclofen treatment.</p>
	<p>[PROC-N3] Administrative procedures Administrative procedures such as discharges, admissions, screenings, notifications,</p>	<p>Cardiology admission in July for problems related to dietary transgressions</p>

	appointments, applications, etc. should not be annotated.	Discharged with follow-up by gastroenterology
	[PROC-N4] Training procedures Training procedures such as teaching, demonstrating or counselling for the purpose of increasing knowledge and skills, triggering a behavioural change, or the assistance in improving the skills to face certain situations and/or improving compliance with treatment or recommendations should not be annotated.	Recommendations to minimise discomfort
	[PROC-N5] Priority Temporal expressions expressing the priority or urgency of the procedures are not included in the annotation: "emergency", "urgent", "routine", "immediate", "scheduled", "control", "follow-up", etc.	Scheduled CT Urgent Laparotomy
	[PROC-N6] Sequence Words referring to the order of the procedures should not be annotated: "first", "initial", etc.	First conjunctival discharge culture grows gonococci
	[PROC-N7] Questionnaires Questionnaires, scales, and assessments (quality of life, geriatric, etc.), which are generally considered observable entities, should not be annotated.	EQ-5D is administered. Presents Glasgow 15/15

	<p>[PROC-N8] Treatment The word treatment is not included in the annotation if it is not essential, nor when the mention of the treatment is highly unspecific.</p>	<p>Good response to treatment with topical corticosteroids.</p> <p>He cannot remember his pharmacological treatment</p> <p>Dyslipidaemia in dietary treatment</p>
	<p>[PROC-N9] Place of application We do not annotate the procedure when only the area of application is indicated.</p>	<p>Did not respond to topical treatment</p> <p>Dyspnoea decreases with intravenous steroid therapy</p>
	<p>[PROC-N10] Oncology cycles In reference to oncological treatments, it should not be annotated whether the treatment is first or second line, nor the number of cycles.</p>	<p>It was decided to start 3rd line chemotherapy with trabectedin and pegylated liposomal adriamycin.</p>
	<p>[PROC-N11] Departments Departmental and speciality names of homonymous procedures shall not be annotated.</p>	<p>A 39-year-old patient is admitted to the vascular surgery department.</p> <p>12 hours after vascular surgery, the patient is transferred home.</p>
<p>Special Rules</p>	<p>[PROC-S1] Verbs I Some procedures may consist of single verbs. This includes conjugated verbs and also impersonal forms (infinitive, gerund and participle). When annotating verbs, particles and auxiliary verbs ("was", "were") should be included in the annotation. However, in the case of verbal</p>	<p>Patient extubated on postoperative day 4.</p>

	<p>periphrases (combination of two verbs, such as "have to + verb"), it is sufficient to annotate the second verb.</p>	
	<p>[PROC-S2] Verbs II If the verb is relevant to determining the type of procedure, it should be included within the annotation. This is very common with devices, which are often accompanied by a verb describing what is done with them ("placed", "removed"). Verbs are annotated as described in the previous rule.</p>	<p>Vaccinated against influenza five days ago</p> <p>PCI with implantation of three drug-eluting stents is performed</p> <p>A 3 x 20 mm everolimus-eluting stent is implanted.</p> <p>We finished by implanting another everolimus stent.</p> <p>Treatment with serotherapy is started</p> <p>According to previously established medical criteria, the therapeutic effort is limited.</p> <p>family members are informed by telephone of the patient's poor general condition and possible poor prognosis given the comorbidity, agreeing not to take aggressive measures.</p> <p>presented progressive clinical worsening and comfort measures were initiated, being exitus vitae on 15 October.</p> <p>Counterpulsation balloon implanted via right femoral access without incident.</p> <p>The rectal ampulla is explored by retroversion.</p>

	<p>[PROC-S3] Temporality Although time expressions should generally not be annotated, they are included when they are part of the name of the procedure.</p>	<p>Right ureterolithotomy 10 years earlier 24-hour urine catecholamines</p>
	<p>[PROC-S4] Daily Subsistence Allowance Diets should be recorded as procedures.</p>	<p>Lactose-free and gluten-free diet KETO Diet</p>
	<p>[PROC-S5] Perfusions and boluses Mentions of specific drugs are annotated when administered in pump, bolus or infusion form.</p>	<p>Anticoagulation with perfused sodium heparin. Reversed with bolus and amiodarone perfusion furosemide 40mg bolus started</p>
	<p>[PROC-S6] Monitoring Vital signs surveillance with the assistance of monitoring equipment shall be annotated as a procedure.</p>	<p>He remains under continuous monitoring of haemodynamic constants for 48 hours.</p>
	<p>[PROC-S7] Ventilation The FiO2 settings at which they are used (21, 28, 31, 35, 40, 60) should be included in the annotations for oxygen masks, venturi masks and Ventimask. This does not apply to high-flow or nasal contact therapies, nor does it apply to Monaghan.</p>	<p>Ventimask at 50% FiO2 was started in the pneumology ward under monitoring. good saturations (97-98%) with VMK 31-35%. Also requires high-flow therapy at 60%/50L</p>

	<p>[PROC-S8] Resistors References to the fact that the procedure is focused on the detection of resistance and sensitivities, as well as references to specific pathogens, should be included in the annotation.</p>	<p>Nasal swab (MRSA/MSSA) (01/08/2015): ...</p> <p>Smear for the detection of multi-resistant GNBs</p> <p>positive rapid streptococcal test on tonsillar exudate</p> <p>Vaginal and rectal smear for group B streptococcus detection</p>
	<p>[PROC-S9] Brands The equipment and material brands used during procedures should be annotated only when deemed necessary and in their shortest form, and when the brand is synonymous with the type of procedure (see Ventimask).</p>	<p>Ventimask is maintained until normalisation of saturations.</p> <p>(In the example above, although Ventimask is a brand name, it is still annotated as it is used as a synonym for a Venturi mask.)</p> <p>To stimulate the nuclei located in the rhomboid fossa, we used the NIM-Response® Nerve Monitoring System (Medtronic, XOMED).</p> <p>Reintubation and connection to mechanical ventilation (Babylog 8000 plus, Dräger Medizintechnik GMBH. Lübeck, Germany) was required.</p> <p>Inguinal hernia correction with marlex mesh</p>
	<p>[PROC-S10] Specials The "optimisation of anaemia" (generally pre-surgical), as well as its most frequent treatment (iron + EPO), should be annotated as a procedure. Similarly, "off pump" (cardiac) will be interpreted</p>	<p>Optimisation of anaemia due to inflammatory process is carried out</p> <p>came off-pump in sinus rhythm with haemodynamic support</p>

	as weaning and should also be annotated.	
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6. RULES FOR DRUGS

	Rule	Example
Label DRUG		
Positive Rules	<p>[DRUG-P1] Drug names All specific products, compounds or substances with a defined molecular composition and a therapeutic purpose are annotated.</p>	<p>diclofenac insulin oxygen calcium</p>
	<p>[DRUG-P2] Trade names Trade names of drugs are also annotated. If a trade name appears together with a generic name, they are annotated separately.</p>	<p>baclofen (Lioresal®)</p>
	<p>[DRUG-P3] Common combinations Common drug combinations are annotated as a single entity when they appear as a single word. To find out whether a combination is common or not, we can consult SNOMED CT or the AEMPS (https://cima.aemps.es/cima/publico/lista.html).</p>	<p>amoxicillin-clavulanic acid lopinavir/ritonavir Piperacillin-tazobactam</p>

	<p>[DRUG-P4] Abbreviations Abbreviated drug names are sometimes found, especially when several drugs are administered together. These abbreviations should also be annotated whenever we know unequivocally that they refer to a drug.</p>	<p>lopirito (lopinavir + ritonavir) L/r (lopinavir + ritonavir) Pipertazo (piperacillin + tazobactam) LPV/r + HCQ + azithromycin</p>
Negative Rules	<p>[DRUG-N1] Non-therapeutic purposes Substances used for non-therapeutic purposes are not annotated, even if they are sometimes used for therapeutic purposes. Examples include: compounds and elements used for diagnostic purposes and substance preparation, disinfection of operating rooms, contrast media, antiseptics not applied directly to the patient, substances measured in analytical tests, etc.</p>	<p>Deficient calcium levels</p> <p>On day 5, a cardiac MRI was performed, which confirmed myopericarditis with late subepicardial gadolinium enhancement.</p>
	<p>[DRUG-N2] General types of pharmaceuticals General types and families of substances are not annotated as drugs. These types of mentions should be annotated as procedures.</p>	<p>Currently on corticosteroids treatment</p> <p>Antiviral treatment</p> <p>Appropriate antibiotic prophylaxis</p> <p>Depletive treatment is started with a good response.</p>
	<p>[DRUG-N3] Power Drug power is not annotated (g, mg, etc.).</p>	<p>Amlodipine 10 mg</p> <p>Bisoprolol normon 2.5 mg film-coated tablets</p>

	[DRUG-N4] Dosage Drug dosage is not annotated.	Azithromycin 250 mg, once daily, at breakfast Paracetamol kern pharma 1000 mg tablets efg, 40 tablets.1000 M G. Oral use. Every 8 hours. IF NEEDED
	[DRUG-N5] Pharmaceutical forms The drug formulation is not included in the annotation.	tablet, capsule, sachet, ointment
	[DRUG-N6] Administration method The drug administration method is not annotated.	oral, dermal
Special Rules	[DRUG-S1] Conventions To homogenise the annotation criteria, we will always annotate these substances as drugs: heparin, insulin, chemical elements administered for therapeutic purposes (calcium, phosphorus, potassium, etc.), vitamins (vitamin A, B, C, etc.),	Intravenous magnesium, calcium and potassium replacement with progressive improvement. Insulin treatment is started during admission
	[DRUG-S2] Percentage of serums and eye drops As an exception to the power and dosage rules, in eye drops and serums we do annotate the percentage of the substances in the eye drops and serums.	Treatment with Mitomycin-C 0.02% preoperatively
	[DRUG-S3] Immunoglobulins and Plasma The administration of immunoglobulins and	Intravenous immunoglobulin is administered for 5 days and treatment according to the protocol for COVID-19 patients with

	convalescent plasma is annotated as a drug.	hydroxychloroquine sulphate , antiretrovirals (lopinavir and ritonavir), antibiotics (amoxicillin), corticosteroids and low-flow oxygen therapy.
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7. RULES FOR SPECIES

	Rule	Example
Label SPECIES		
Positive Rules	<p>[SPE-P1] Pathogens and Living Organisms Microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, microbes, parasites) as well as animals and plants are annotated with this label.</p> <p>*As an exception, we do not annotate mentions of humans as they have their own label.</p> <p>Rules SPE-S8 to SPE-S12 provide further details on the annotation of microorganisms.</p>	<p>Referred exposure to sheep when she was young</p> <p>Has not bathed in fresh water, has not had contact with animals</p> <p>PRESENCE OF OCCASIONAL MICROORGANISMS (SPORES) WITH THE SILVER STAIN</p> <p>Nasal swab (MRSA/MSSA)(14/03/2018): normal flora is found</p> <p>URINOCULTURE (11/3): They are between 10,000 and 100,000 CFU/mL. Mixed flora</p> <p>Immunohistochemical staining for herpesvirus I and II, cytomegalovirus, parvovirus B19, HIV (P24), toxoplasma and in situ hybridisation for Epstein Barr virus are negative.</p> <p>Sediment rich in Yeast</p>
	<p>[SPE-P2] Specific and general species Both should be annotated: <u>specific species names</u> (e.g. "Aspergillus</p>	<p>Medical grow for common bacteria, including Neiseria and Haemophilus,</p>

	<p>fumigatus", "Klebsiella", "Pseudomonas", "Staphylococcus aureus") and</p> <p><u>general names for types of species</u> (e.g. "mycobacteria", "fungi", "anaerobes", "helminths").</p>	<p>Two strains of coagulase negative Staphylococcus (identified as Staphylococcus epidermidis and alpha haemolytic Streptococcus) are found</p> <p>Blood determination of antibodies (ELISA) and determination of virus existence (HTLV-I)</p> <p>Negative VDRL</p> <p>Gram staining: Gram-positive cocci of the staphylococcus type are observed.</p>
	<p>[SPE-P3] Taxonomic Root Words that contain a taxonomic word of a species in the root regardless of the context are annotated, except when they refer to specific drugs (penicillin, streptomycin).</p>	<p>Antiviral, antifungal, antibrucella, antituberculosis, antiretroviral, antitetanus, tuberculostatic</p>
	<p>[SPE-P4] Derived words Words derived from taxonomic entities are annotated regardless of context, except when they refer to specific drugs (penicillin, streptomycin).</p>	<p>abundant bacteriuria</p> <p>polymicrobial growth</p> <p>With suspected subacute bacterial endocarditis</p> <p>Suspecting acute glomerulonephritis (GN), probably post-infectious</p>

	<p>[SPE-P5] Vulgar Both taxonomic and common names should be recorded. In the case where the Latin taxonomic and common names appear together, they shall be annotated separately.</p>	<p>Staphylococcus, Trypanosoma brucei (taxonomic names) sleeping sickness parasite (common names) ...wasp venom (Vespula spp.) < 0.1 kU/L</p>
	<p>[SPE-P6] Figurative mentions Mentions that refer to a species and are used figuratively should also be annotated.</p>	<p>On examination, he presents multiple facial injuries with a butterfly wing distribution, flat in appearance. She is considered the "black sheep" of the family. ...in layers of onion...</p>
	<p>[SPE-P7] Food Plants and animals which are likely to be food shall be annotated.</p>	<p>We recommend a diet of boiled or mashed potatoes. he went to the doctor and was diagnosed with fish poisoning.</p>
Negative Rules	<p>[SPE-N1] Fantastic Creatures References to fantastic creatures, supernatural and religious entities should not be annotated.</p>	<p>His favourite animal is the unicorn. She has visions with angels and demons.</p>
	<p>[SPE-N2] Homonyms Words that are homonyms (spelled and pronounced the same) to species should not be annotated when it is not clear that they refer to an organism.</p>	<p>Orange stain (The word "orange" can be a colour or a fruit. As in this case it refers to the colour, it is not annotated).</p>

	<p>[SPE-N3] Homonyms The word "toxin" on its own may refer to several bacteria and requires too much inference on the part of the annotator, so it is not annotated. However, it is annotated when accompanied (e.g. "botulinum toxin").</p>	No toxins or parasites were investigated.
Special Rules	<p>[SPE-S1] Mentions without code The following terms are annotated, even if they do not have a specific code in the NCBI Taxonomy: 'strains', 'colonies', 'hepatotropic viruses', 'hepatitis viruses', 'parasites', 'bacilli', 'gram positive bacilli'.</p>	<p>mixed aerobic flora GP and GN</p> <p>Normal or saprophytic flora</p>
	<p>[SPE-S2] Vectors When the word "vector" is associated with a species, the two entities should be annotated separately. Other epidemiologically relevant terms such as 'host', 'intermediate host', 'vector', 'pathogen reservoir', 'outbreaks' and exact synonyms should also be annotated.</p>	Plasmodium was found in the mosquito vector (Anopheles) .
	<p>[SPE-S3] Drugs Mentions of drugs of abuse that are also plants (marijuana, cannabis, tobacco) are annotated, but not those that require a pharmacological process for their production (cocaine, heroin).</p>	Regular cannabis user
	<p>[SPE-S4] Conventions To homogenise the annotation criteria, the</p>	Other bacterial, fungal, parasitic , and other pathogens

	<p>following words are annotated: "pathogens", "organisms", "microorganisms", "microbiota", "microbiome", "virology", "bacteriology".</p> <p>Similarly, "microbiology", "antibiotic", "asepsis" and "antiseptis", as well as words derived from these terms, should not be annotated.</p>	<p>PRESENCE OF MICROORGANISMS WITH SILVER STAINING MORPHOLOGICALLY COMPATIBLE WITH FUNGI</p>
	<p>[SPE-S5] Vaccines The word "vaccine" and the different forms of the verb "vaccinate" shall be annotated, together with the type of vaccine, where applicable.</p>	<p>Routine vaccinations up to date, plus pneumococcal vaccine referral for 67-year-old female patient admitted for SARS-COV-2 infection (unvaccinated)</p>
	<p>[SPE-S6] Pro- and prebiotics We will annotate the word probiotic (live microorganisms, predominantly bacteria and fungi) and its derivatives, but not the word prebiotic (food components) and derivatives.</p>	<p>Diarrhoea secondary to antibiotics, so a probiotic was added.</p>
	<p>[SPE-S7] Multi resistors and sensitivities We will include the word "multidrug-resistant" in the annotations, but not the word "multi-sensitive", which we consider to be a basic condition of a pathogen. We also annotate: "coagulase negative staphylococcus", "MRSA staphylococcus".</p>	<p>Multiresistant flora isolation of sensible K. pneumoniae and pseudomonas aeruginosa Rectal smear. Detected multiresistent GNBs (14/03/2018): Negative MRSA nasal swab (9.11): negative</p>

	<p>[SPE-S8] Bacteria With regard to bacteria, we should annotate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Antimicrobial resistance and sensitivities. b) Morphologies, specific stains, biochemical identification, special growth requirements. c) Non-taxonomic classifications d) Genotypes, serotypes and strains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) "Enterobacteriaceae BLEE, MRSA, morganella morganii phenotype AmpC", etc. <p>AMP C chromosomal beta-lactamase overproducing Enterobacter cloacae complex Soca</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> b) "gram-positive/negative bacilli", "coagulase-negative staphylococcus", "multidrug-resistant S. epidermidis", 'gram-negative pleomorphic bacillus', 'gram+ and gram-anaerobic bacilli', 'gram-negative aerobic facultative bacilli', 'slow-growing bacteria', 'pyogenic bacteria', 'gram-negative coccobacillus', 'catalase positive', 'oxidase positive', 'gram positive cocci in clusters', etc. <p>We can observe gram positive cocci</p> <p>acid-alcohol-resistant bacilli</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> c) "vaginal flora", "normal bacterial flora of the oral cavity", "mixed saprophytic flora", "germs of the oral and vaginal flora", etc. <p>BAS (16/5/2016): normal or saprophyte flora</p>
	<p>[SPE-S9] Virus With regard to viruses, we should annotate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Affected systems. b) Genotypes, serotypes and strains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) "cardiotropic, neurotropic viruses"

	<p>[SPE-S10] Fungi With regard to fungi, we should annotate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Resistances and sensitivities. b) Mycotic morphology and structures c) Other non-taxonomic classifications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) "azole-sensitive <i>Candida albicans</i>", etc. b) "hyphae", 'septate hyphae', 'conidia', 'conidiophores', 'spores', 'microconidia', 'mycelium', 'levaduriform', 'sympodial conidiation', 'black fungal colony', etc. c) "opportunistic", "true", "dematiaceous", "pathogenic", "filamentous", "hyphomycetes", etc.
	<p>[SPE-S11] Parasites With regard to parasites, we should annotate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Parasitic forms of biological cycles. b) Parasite-related structures c) Type/form of parasitism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) "eggs", "adult specimen*", "cyst", "trophozoite", "miracidium", "schistocyte", "larva", "amastigote", "trypomastigote", "cercaria", "sporocyst", "redia", "nymph", "nymph", ... b) "Scolex", "proglottide", etc. ** c) "intra-erythrocyte ring parasites", etc. <p>* Only annotated for parasites and accompanied by a qualifier. ** Excludes: "mute", "vestige", "appendix".</p>
	<p>[SPE-S12] Prions Prions should also be annotated</p>	<p>Dementia was caused by prions; signs of accelerated dementia pointed to Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease.</p>
	<p>[SPE-S13] COVID/SARS Mentions of SARS (and spelling variants) are always annotated as species, while the word COVID (and variants) are considered diseases.</p>	

8. RULES FOR HUMANS

	Rule	Example
Label HUMAN		
Positive Rules	<p>[HUM-P1] Human Words referring to humans in a general way should be annotated: "human", "patient", "person", etc., as well as to groups of people: "family".</p>	36-year-old patient
	<p>[HUM-P2] Family members Nouns and adjectives referring to family relationships ("mother", "sister", "grandmother", "niece", etc.), as well as positions within the family (e.g., "the little one") should be annotated. If the branch of the family (maternal/paternal) is mentioned, it should be included in the annotation.</p>	<p>Infant, Caucasian, the first child of young parents (mother 28 years old and father 30 years old).</p> <p>The paternal uncle had been diagnosed with...</p> <p>The eldest of three siblings experienced seizures.</p>
	<p>[HUM-P3] Life Stages The different stages of life should be annotated when they appear in substantive form: "youth", "childhood", "adolescence", "old age"</p>	<p>Pulmonary tuberculosis in childhood</p> <p>Gunshot wound to the thorax in youth</p>
	<p>[HUM-P4] Sex and Gender Words referring to a person's sex or gender</p>	56-year-old male that comes because...

	<p>should be annotated.</p> <p>If one of these words appears together with the word "patient", both words shall be annotated as a single entity.</p>	<p>Female patient, 62 years of age, obese, diabetic, and hypertensive, one year old.</p>
	<p>[HUM-P5] Marital status Nouns referring to a person's marital status ("single", "widowed", "divorced", etc.) should be annotated.</p>	<p>An 81-year-old widow with...</p>
	<p>[HUM-P6] Professions Professions should be annotated substantively, as well as teams and groups of professionals.</p>	<p>She works as a cardiologist in a local hospital.</p> <p>He started working as a street sweeper last October.</p> <p>The team of oncologists took the decision to...</p>
Negative Rules	<p>[HUM-N1] Word "human" The word <i>human</i> should not be annotated when referring to receptors, hormones, etc.</p>	<p>Human epidermal growth factor</p>
	<p>[HUM-N2] Pronouns and adjectives Pronouns and indefinite adjectives referring to persons ("some", "someone", "nobody") should not be annotated.</p>	<p>You don't know anyone in the city yet</p>
	<p>[HUM-N3] Demonyms No general geographic references or names should be annotated.</p>	<p>42-year-old Scottish patient</p>

	<p>[HUM-N4] Health status Adjectives referring to a person's state of health (including "pregnant"), to a disease ("hypertensive") or to a habit ("smoker") should not be annotated.</p>	The patient was pregnant , a smoker and hypertensive .
	<p>[HUM-N5] Professionals The words "superior" or "boss" should not be annotated in a professional context.</p>	His bosses considered that the patient should not go to the emergency department.
Special Rules	<p>[HUM-S1] "Family" The word "family" should be annotated in all contexts. As in HUM-P2, if the branch of the family appears, it should be included in the annotation.</p>	He had a family history of diabetes. Maternal family branch
	<p>[HUM-S2] Contacts The word "contact", which is of great importance in the context of infectious diseases, should be annotated when it appears to refer to a person. We will also annotate other concepts of epidemiological interest such as: "reservoirs", "carriers" (of pathogens only), "contacts", "populations", "travellers", etc.</p>	Her partner was the positive contact that forced her into voluntary isolation. His family confirmed previous contact two days before admission. Smear positive for covid-19 , without clinical signs (denies fever, cough, dyspnoea or epidemiological contacts).
	<p>[HUM-S3] Compound words Compound words consisting of two or more words that refer to human should be annotated.</p>	Mother-and-child hospital. Socio-family background

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